

Catalytic aerobic oxidative transformation of the phenolic 9,10-dihydro-phenanthropyran derivative imbricatin with CuCl(OH).TMEDA (TMEDA = *N,N*-tetramethylethylenediamine)[†]

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Abstract : Treatment of imbricatin (2,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran with CuCl(OH).TMEDA (TMEDA = *N,N*-tetramethylethylenediamine) in CH₂Cl₂ at 0–10 °C for 20 h with stirring afforded four different compounds A, B, C and D in relatively low yields. The structures of A, B, C and D were established as 2-hydroxy-6,7-methylenedioxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran (2), 2,2',7,7'-tetrahydroxy-6,6'-dimethoxy-9,9',10,10'-tetrahydro-5*H*,5'*H*-phenanthro[4,4',5,5'-*bcd*]1,1'-bipyranyl (7), 2,2',7,7'-tetrahydroxy-6,6'-dimethoxy-9,9',10,10'-tetrahydro-5*H*,5'*H*-phenanthro[4,4',5,5'-*bcd*]1,3'-bipyranyl (8) and 2,2',7,7'-tetrahydroxy-6,6'-dimethoxy-9,9',10,10'-tetrahydro-5*H*,5'*H*-phenanthro[4,4',5,5'-*bcd*]1,8'-bipyranyl (9), respectively, by spectral and chemical evidence.

Keywords : Imbricatin, naturally occurring phenolic 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyran derivative, oxidative transformation, CuCl(OH).TMEDA, 2-hydroxy-6,7-methylenedioxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran, 1,1'-, 1,3'- and 1,8'-dimers of imbricatin.

Introduction

Oxidative coupling of phenolic compounds is a very old reaction^{1a-c} which provides a simple method for making an aryl-aryl bond. But initially the reaction failed to create any significant impact as a good synthetic method due to relatively poor yield and because of extensive polymerization and lack of regioselectivity. Later the reaction evoked renewed interest for the fact that the biogenesis of a large number of polyphenolics and a variety of tetrahydroisoquinoline alkaloids were assumed^{2a-e} to involve enzymatic oxidative phenol-coupling reaction as an obligatory step. This has led to extensive studies³⁻¹⁹ with several oxidants, viz. FeCl₃⁵, alkaline K₃[Fe(CN)₆]³⁻⁶, [Fe^{III}(DMF)₃Cl₂][Fe^{III}Cl₄]⁷, [Fe^{III}(bipy)₃](ClO₄)₃⁸, MnO₂⁹, Mn^{III}-tris-acetyl acetonate (MTA)¹⁰, Ag₂CO₃, AgNO₃ on celite¹¹, Ag₂O¹², VCl₄¹³, VOCl₃^{13,14}, VOF₃¹⁵, Ti-tris-trifluoroacetate (TIFA)¹⁶, ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN)¹⁷, diacetoxyiodobenzene (DAIB)¹⁸, Cu^{II}-amine complexes¹⁹ and several other oxidants, resulting in the

biomimetic synthesis of a fairly large number of natural products and their synthetic analogues *albeit* in poor to moderate yields. Later this reaction has been used to prepare axially chiral biaryls which are used in organic synthesis as chirality inducers²⁰. But no significant breakthrough in regard to the yields and regioselectivity of the reaction could be achieved till the end of 1980's. In the early 1990's we developed a surface-mediated oxidative phenol-coupling reaction²¹ which involved phosphomolybdic acid (PMA) adsorbed on silica gel. Using this reagent we have been able to achieve^{21,22} regioselective biomimetic synthesis of several naturally occurring phenolic biphenanthyrls and some of their structural analogues from their respective natural phenolic monomers in amazingly high yields (80–95%). 2-Naphthol was almost quantitatively converted²¹ to its 1,1'-dimer with this reagent. However, with simple phenols, this reagent did not work well, and was found to be highly satisfactory. If the site of dimerization is doubly activated with electron-

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donating groups like OH and OMe at the *ortho* and *para* position. Electron-withdrawing groups tend to retard the reaction. In 1994 Noji *et al.*²³ also reported a very elegant method for catalytic aerobic oxidative coupling of phenols with CuCl(OH).TMEDA. Using this reagent they were able to convert²³ 2-naphthol and four of its derivatives to the corresponding 1,1'-dimers in very high yields (90–96%). 9-Phenanthrol was also converted²³ to the corresponding 10,10'-dimer in 79% yield with this reagent. We have also applied²⁴ this reagent to simple phenols like phenol itself, catechol, resorcinol and pyrogallol yielding respective 2,4'-, 4,4'- and 4,4'-, 2,4'- and 4,5'-dimers in poor to moderate yields. Using this reagent we have also converted²⁴ the naturally occurring phenanthrols nudol (2,7-dihydroxy-3,4-dimethoxyphenanthrene), 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene and cirrhoptalin (7-hydroxy-4-methoxy-2,3-methylenedioxyphenanthrene) to the respective 1,1'-, 1,1'- and 8,8'-dimers in 76%, 73% and 66% yields, respectively. As part of our general programme of research on oxidative phenol-coupling reaction^{21,22,24,25}, we have now applied the above reagent to the naturally occurring 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyran derivative imbricatin (**1**) (2,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran)⁶. Treatment of imbricatin (**1**) with CuCl(OH).TMEDA afforded one monomeric (**2**) and three dimeric products (**7**, **8** and **9**) in poor to moderate yields. In this paper we report the results of this investigation and characterization of the above products.

Results and discussion

Imbricatin (**1**)²⁶ in CH₂Cl₂, on stirring with catalytic amount of CuCl(OH).TMEDA at 0–10 °C for 20 h, afforded four compounds A, B, C and D in varying yields. Compound A, analysed for C₁₆H₁₂O₄ (confirmed by its FAB MS). It showed UV absorptions at λ_{max} (EtOH) 218, 282 and 306 nm (log ε 4.65, 4.20 and 3.98) which are strikingly similar to those of imbricatin (**1**)²⁶ itself. The IR spectrum of the compound exhibited a band at ν_{max} 3480 cm⁻¹ for nonchelated hydroxyl function, besides bands for aromatic nucleus. The ¹H NMR spectrum of compound A showed a four-proton ill-resolved multiplet at δ 2.80 which is typical²⁶ of the four benzylic protons of a 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivative. The spectrum, in addition, exhibited a two-proton singlet at δ

5.94 which is characteristic of an aromatic methylenedioxy function. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound also showed signals at δ 5.13 (2H, s) and 5.34 (1H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange) for the two benzylic protons of an oxymethylene group of a pyran system and a phenolic hydroxyl function, respectively. The appearance of the signals at δ 6.33 (2H, ill-resolved br. signal) and 6.62 (1H, s) in the spectrum of compound A indicated the presence of three aromatic protons. The chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of these aromatic protons of compound A are strikingly similar to those of H-1, H-3 and H-8 of imbricatin indicating that compound A essentially differs from imbricatin (**1**) by the replacement of the methoxyl group at C-6 and the hydroxyl function at C-7 of the latter by a methylenedioxy function at C-6 and C-7 in the former. The structure of compound A is thus established as 2-hydroxy-6,7-methylenedioxy-9,10-dihydro-5*H*-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran (**2**).

The formation of **2** from imbricatin (**1**) in the above reaction is a unique observation involving the conversion of a methoxyl group and a phenolic hydroxyl function *ortho* to each other to a methylenedioxy and is mechanistically highly interesting. Two mechanisms may be envisaged for this conversion. In one of these plausible mechanisms the methoxyl function at C-6 of imbricatin (**1**) may be assumed to be intermolecularly oxidized to a hydroxyoxymethylene (ArOMe → Ar-OCH₂OH) group by CuCl(OH).TMEDA, which is then converted to an oxonium ion **a**. The latter may undergo intramolecular cyclisation with the adjacent phenolic hydroxyl group at C-7 to give the methylenedioxy function at C-6 and C-7 as shown in Scheme 1. In an alternative mechanistic pathway for this conversion it was assumed that a hydroperoxy group may be generated at the benzylic oxymethylene C-5 of imbricatin (**1**) by the action of CuCl(OH).TMEDA. This hydroperoxy function (as shown in the species **b**) generated at C-5 of **1** being in close proximity to the OMe group at C-6 (in the particular conformation of **1** as shown in Scheme 1) may oxidize it intramolecularly by a Barton-type remote-control functionalization reaction to a hydroxyoxymethylene group which is then converted to a similar oxonium species **b'** as in the case of the other mechanism. Nucleophilic attack by the adjacent phenolic hydroxyl function on the oxonium ion **b'** may finally gene-

rate the methylenedioxy function as shown in Scheme 1. Reduction of the lactol intermediate **c** may finally give **2**. In order to make a decision between the two alternative mechanisms compound **3** prepared by reduction of vanillin in excess methanol was treated with $\text{CuCl}(\text{OH})$. TMEDA followed by NaBH_4 to give only the 6,6'-dimer of **3** (**4**) and no compound like **5** or **6** containing methylenedioxy function (Scheme 1). Compound **3** may also form a hydroperoxy group at its benzylic carbon atom. But such a hydroperoxy group, if at all formed, being much away from the methoxyl group would be unable to oxidize the methoxyl function intramolecularly. The above observations thus provide strong evidence in support of the second mechanism of formation of the methylenedioxy function involving intramolecular oxidation of the methoxyl group rather than an intermolecular

oxidation as envisaged in the first mechanism. The formation of **2** in the above oxidation reaction of imbricatin (**1**) thus provides the most convincing evidence in support of the biogenesis of the methylenedioxy group in a number of natural products assumed to involve similar reaction *albeit* enzymatically.

All the remaining three compounds B, C and D isolated as amorphous powder are isomeric having the molecular formula $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8$, confirmed by their similar FAB mass spectra indicating a molecular weight of 538 for all the three compounds. This would suggest that all the three compounds are dimers of imbricatin (**1**) dimerized in three different ways. The UV spectra of the compounds showed absorption maxima similar to those of **1**. The IR spectra of the compounds exhibited strong absorption band at

Scheme 1. Mechanism of formation of compound A (2).

ν_{max} 3400–3450 cm^{-1} for phenolic hydroxyl groups, besides usual bands for aromatic nucleus. Theoretically there can be six possible dimers of 1, viz. 1,1'-, 3,3'-, 8,8'-, 1,3'-, 1,8'- and 3,8'-dimers, since C-1, C-3 and C-8 are

the only three carbon atoms in imbricatin, which are *ortho* to a phenolic hydroxyl group. Of the six possible dimers of 1,1'-, 3,3'- and 8,8'-dimers are symmetrical, while the remaining three (1,3'-, 1,8'- and 3,8'-dimers) are unsym-

metrical. The actual structures of compounds B, C and D were established mainly from their ^1H NMR spectral data.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of compound B showed 7 sets of signals at δ 2.54 (m), 2.72 (m), 3.80 (s), 5.27 (s), 5.56 (br. s), 6.58 (s) and 6.73 (s) in the integral ratio of 2:2:3:2:2:1:1. Since B contains a total number of 26 protons, each of these signals must correspond to double the number of protons given by their respective integral ratio. This, in turn, indicates the symmetrical dimeric structure of the compound. Compound B may, therefore, be any one of the symmetrical dimers of imbricatin (**1**), viz. 1,1'-, 3,3'- and 8,8'-. A decision between the three possibilities could be made by the ^1H NMR spectral data of the compound. Thus the signals at δ 3.80 (6H, s) and 5.56 (4H, br. signal; disappeared on deuterium exchange) indicate the presence of two aromatic methoxyl groups and four phenolic hydroxyl functions in compound B. The signals at δ 2.54 (4H, m) and 2.72 (4H, m) corresponding to two sets of four benzylic protons of two 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene units resemble those of H₂-9 and H₂-10 of imbricatin (**1**) *albeit* resonating at relatively higher field than those of **1**. The presence of two pyran moieties in A was indicated by the appearance of the signal at δ 5.27 (4H, s) in the ^1H NMR spectrum of the compound, which corresponds to the four protons of the two benzylic oxymethylene groups associated with the two pyran units. The ^1H NMR spectrum of compound B also showed signals at δ 6.58 (2H, s) and 6.73 (2H, s), each corresponding to a pair of equivalent aromatic protons, of which the signal at δ 6.73 is strikingly similar to that of H-8 of **1**. Accordingly, the signal at δ 6.73 may be assigned to H-8 and H-8' of compound B. This, in turn, rules out the 8,8'-dimeric formulation of the compound. Compound B may, therefore, be either a 1,1'- or 3,3'-dimer of imbricatin (**1**) and accordingly the aromatic proton signal of B at δ 6.58 (2H, s) may be attributed to either H-3 and H-3' or H-1 and H-1' depending on the mode of dimerization through C-1 or C-3 of imbricatin (**1**). The downfield shift of the signal at δ 6.58 by 0.25 ppm compared to those of H-1 and H-3 of **1** may be attributed to the introduction of an aromatic substituent at C-1 or C-3 of B. The exact site of dimerization in B (and also in C and D) was ascertained by a critical examination of the conformational structure of the compound (and also those of C and D).

Construction of Dreiding model of the compound B shows that in the most preferred conformation of the compound the two monomeric halves of the compound remain almost perpendicular to each other. As a result H₂-10 and H₂-10' of B fall in the shielding zones of the phenyl rings A' and A, respectively. This would cause a shielding of the above four protons of compound B. Similarly, H₂-9 and H₂-9' of the compound also experience a long range shielding by the phenyl rings A' and A, respectively. Since these four protons of compound B are at larger distance from the shielding zones of rings A' and A than those of H₂-10 and H₂-10', shielding of H₂-9 and H₂-9' would be less than those of H₂-10 and H₂-10'.

The signals at δ 2.54 (4H, s) and 2.72 (4H, s) may, therefore, be assigned to H₂-10 and H₂-10' and H₂-9 and H₂-9', respectively. This, in turn, also establishes the site of dimerization in compound B to be at C-1 and C-1'. The aromatic proton signal at δ 6.58 may then be assigned to H-3 and H-3'. In the alternative 3,3'-dimeric formulation of B, H₂-9 and H₂-9' and H₂-10 and H₂-10' would have resonated at the normal region (similar to H₂-9 and H₂-10 of imbricatin) and both H₂-5 and H₂-5' would have been shielded. Again, in the 8,8'-dimeric formulation of B, H-3, H-3' and H-1, H-1' would have resonated at the normal region (*ca.* δ 6.30) similar to H-3 and H-1 of imbricatin. The structure of compound B is, thus established as **7**.

Now, coming to compounds C and D, the ^1H NMR spectrum of C, on the other hand, showed 13 sets of signals at δ 2.63 (m), 2.72 (m), 2.89 (m), 3.75 (s), 3.80 (s), 4.92 (br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange), 5.16 (br. s), 5.26 (distorted ABq), 5.51 (br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange), 6.58 (s), 6.60 (s), 6.73 (s) and 6.77 (s) in the integral ratio of 2:2:4:3:3:2:2:2:1:1:1:1 and that of compound D exhibited 10 sets of signals at δ 2.52 (m), 2.64 (m), 3.92 (s), 3.98 (s), 4.91 (br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange), 5.26 (br. s), 5.51 (br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange), 6.33 (br. signal), 6.57 (s) and 6.67 (s) in the integral ratio of 4:4:3:3:2:4:2:2:1:1. Since both the compounds contain 26 protons, each signal of both C and D corresponds to the same number of proton(s) given by their integral ratio. This, in turn, also indicates that both the compounds must be unsymmetrical dimers. So they must be any two of the three

possible unsymmetrical dimers of imbricatin (**1**), viz. 1,3'-, 1,8'- and 3,8'-dimers of **1**. Here again, a decision could be arrived at by the ^1H NMR spectral data of compounds C and D. Thus the signals at δ 3.75 (3H, s) and 3.80 (3H, s) and 4.92 and 5.51 (each 2H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange) displayed by the ^1H NNIR spectrum of C established the presence of two aromatic methoxyl groups and four phenolic hydroxyl functions, respectively, in compound C. Similarly the presence of two aromatic methoxyl and four phenolic hydroxyl groups also in compound D was confirmed by the appearance of the signals at δ 3.92 (3H, s) and 3.98 (3H, s), and 4.92 and 5.51 (each 2H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange), respectively, in the ^1H NMR spectrum of D. The sites of dimerization in C and D were ascertained by a critical analysis of the chemical shifts of the four benzylic methylene protons of the two 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene units, the protons of the two oxymethylene groups of the two pyran moieties and the four aromatic protons of the two compounds in the light of their preferred conformations, in which the two monomeric halves are almost perpendicular to each other as in the case of compound B. In the light of the above contention the chemical shifts of the above protons of compounds C and D are only intelligible in terms of the 1,3'- and 1,8'-dimeric structures **8** and **9**, respectively, for the two compounds.

Thus, of the eight benzylic protons of the two 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene units of compound C (**8**), four associated with one of these units resonated at the normal region (δ 2.89). So the signal at δ 2.89 of compound C may be assigned to its $\text{H}_2\text{-9'}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{-10'}$, which being far away from the other 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene unit resonated at the normal region similar to that of the corresponding protons of imbricatin (δ 2.81). The remaining four such benzylic protons of C are shifted upfields to δ 2.63 and 2.72 (each 2H, m), since they fall in the shielding zone of the phenyl ring A' of the other 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene unit. The above signals at δ 2.63 and 2.72 may, therefore, be assigned to $\text{H}_2\text{-10}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{-9}$ of compound C (**8**). This implies that of the two molecules of imbricatin (**1**) only C-1 of one has been involved in its dimerization to compound C (**8**). The appearance of the signals at δ 6.77 (1H, s) and 6.73 (1H, s) in the ^1H NMR spectrum of C, which strikingly resemble that of H-8 of imbricatin (**1**) rules out the involvement of C-8 of

imbricatin in its dimerization to compound C (**8**). The signals at δ 6.77 and 6.73 may, therefore, be assigned to H-8 and H-8' of compound C (**8**). This, in turn, implies that the second site of dimerization must be the C-3 (C-3' of C) of imbricatin thereby affirming the 1,3'-dimeric formulation of compound C (**8**). This was evident from the appearance of the signals at δ 6.58 (1H, s) and 6.60 (1H, s) in the ^1H NMR spectrum of C, which by analogy with the signal at δ 6.58 (H-3, H-3') of compound B (**7**) may be assigned to H-3 and H-1', respectively, of compound C. The most convincing evidence in support of the 1,3'-dimeric formulation of compound C is the upfield shift of the proton of one of the benzylic oxymethylene groups of one of the pyran moieties by 0.1 ppm [δ 5.16 (2H, br. s)], the protons of the other such oxymethylene resonating at the normal region [δ 5.26 2H, distorted ABq]. The upfield signal at δ 5.16 may, therefore, be attributed to $\text{H}_2\text{-5'}$ of compound C, which fall in the shielding zone of the phenyl ring A of the neighbouring 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene unit of the compound. The signal at δ 5.26 resonating at the normal region thus corresponds to $\text{H}_2\text{-5}$ of compound C. The structure of compound C is thus established as **8**.

Now, coming back to the structure of compound D, the upfield shifts of all the eight benzylic protons of the two 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene units of the compound to δ 2.52 and 2.64 (each 4H, m) compared to the corresponding protons of imbricatin (**1**) require the dimerization to take place through C-1 of one molecule of imbricatin and C-8 of the other. The signals at δ 2.52 and 2.64 of compound D may, therefore, be assigned to $\text{H}_2\text{-10}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{-9'}$, and $\text{H}_2\text{-9}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{-10'}$, respectively, which fall in the shielding zones of the phenyl rings C', A, C' and A, respectively. The signal at δ 6.67 (1H, s) of compound D, which resemble that of H-8 of imbricatin may be assigned to H-8 of the compound. The absence of any other signal in the above region indicates that C-8 of another molecule of imbricatin has been involved in the process of its dimerization to compound D. The appearance of the signals for the four protons of the two benzylic oxymethylene groups associated with the two pyran moieties of compound D at the normal region [δ 5.26 (4H, br. s)] ruled out the dimerization in D through C-3 of imbricatin (**1**). The signal at δ 6.33 (2H, br. signal) of D being typical of H-1 and H-3 of imbricatin thus corres-

ponds to H-1' and H-3' of the compound. The remaining aromatic proton signal of D at δ 6.57 (1H, s), may, therefore, be assigned to H-3 of the compound by analogy with the corresponding proton signal of compounds B (7) and C (8). The structure of the compound D is thus established as **9** i.e. 1,8'-dimer of imbricatin (**1**).

Experimental

Melting points : uncorr. CC : silica gel (100–200 mesh). TLC : silica gel G. IR : KBr discs. $^1\text{H NMR}$: 300 Mz. NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 using TMS as the internal standard and chemical shifts were expressed in δ (ppm). MS : direct inlet system, 70 eV. All analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. The petrol used had b.p. 60–80 °C.

Formation of compounds A (2), B (7), C (8) and D (9) in the reaction of imbricatin (1) with CuCl(OH).TMEDA :

To a solution of imbricatin (**1**) (0.3 g) in CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml) was added freshly prepared²³ CuCl(OH).TMEDA (0.05 g) and the mixture was stirred at 0–10 °C for 20 h. To the reaction mixture was then added MeOH (10 ml) and NaBH_4 (0.1 g) in several portions and stirred for a further period of 30 min at room temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with water (20 ml), acidified with dilute HCl and extracted with EtOAc, washed with water, dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel.

The petrol-EtOAc (15 : 1) eluate afforded **2** (0.01 g) as a semisolid mass (Found : C, 71.58; H, 4.47. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 71.61; H, 4.51%); UV : λ_{max} (EtOH) 218, 282 and 306 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.65, 4.20 and 3.98); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3480 (OH); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 2.80 (4H, m; H_2 -9 and H_2 -10), 5.34 (1H, s; disappeared on deuterium exchange; Ar-OH), 5.13 (2H, s; H_2 -5), 5.94 (2H, s; protons of the methylenedioxy group), 6.33 (2H, br. signal; H-1 and H-3) and 6.62 (1H, s; H-8).

The petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate gave unreacted imbricatin (**1**) (0.02 g). Washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (3 : 1) afforded a mixture of **7**, **8** and **9**. Repeated chromatography of this mixture using the same eluent finally afforded pure **7** (0.07 g) in the early fractions, **8** (0.08 g) in the middle fractions and **9** (0.04 g) in the end fractions, each as an amorphous powder.

Compound B (**7**) : (Found : C, 71.29; H, 4.83. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 71.35; H, 4.87%); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 2.54 (4H, m; H_2 -10 and H_2 -10'), 2.72 (4H, m; H_2 -9 and H_2 -9'), 3.80 (6H, s; $2 \times$ Ar-OMe), 5.27 (4H, s; H_2 -5 and H_2 -5'), 5.56 (4H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange; $4 \times$ Ar-OH), 6.58 (2H, s; H-3 and H-3') and 6.73 (2H, s; H-8 and H-8').

Compound C (**8**) : (Found : C, 71.27; H, 4.81. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 71.35; H, 4.87%); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 2.63 (2H, m; H_2 -10), 2.72 (2H, m; H_2 -9), 2.89 (4H, m; H_2 -9' and H_2 -10), 3.75 (3H, s; Ar-OMe), 3.80 (3H, s; Ar-OMe), 4.93 and 4.99 (each 1H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange; $2 \times$ Ar-OH), 5.16 (2H, br. s; H_2 -5'), 5.26 (2H, distorted ABq; H_2 -5), 5.46 (2H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange; $2 \times$ Ar-OH), 6.58 (1H, s; H-3), 6.60 (1H, s; H-3'), 6.73 (1H, s; H-8') and 6.77 (1H, s; H-8).

Compound D (**9**) : (Found : C, 71.25; H, 4.79. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 71.35; H, 4.87%); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 2.52 (4H, m; H_2 -10 and H_2 -10'), 2.64 (4H, m; H_2 -9 and H_2 -9'), 3.92 (3H, s; Ar-OMe), 3.98 (3H, s; Ar-OMe), 4.92 (2H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange; $2 \times$ Ar-OH), 5.26 (4H, br. s; H_2 -5 and H_2 -5'), 5.51 (2H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange; $2 \times$ Ar-OH), 6.33 (2H, br. signal; H-1 and H-3'), 6.57 (1H, s; H-3) and 6.67 (1H, s; H-8).

Formation of 2,2'-dihydroxy-3,3'-dimethoxy-5,5'-di(methoxymethyl)-6,6'-biphenyl (4) from 2-methoxy-4-methoxymethylphenol (3) with CuCl(OH).TMEDA :

To a solution of **3** (0.2 g) (prepared by reduction of vanillin with NaBH_4 in excess of MeOH) in CH_2Cl_2 (30 ml) was added 0.04 g of CuCl(OH).TMEDA and the mixture was stirred at 0–10 °C for 20 h. To the reaction mixture was added 5 ml MeOH and then 0.09 g of NaBH_4 in several portions. The mixture was then stirred at room temperature for another 30 min and worked up in the same manner as described in the reaction of imbricatin. The residue thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel. The petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) eluate afforded **4** (0.16 g) as a semisolid mass (Found : C, 64.59; H, 6.58. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6$ requires : C, 64.64; H, 6.63%); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 6.96 (2H, d, J 1.64 Hz; H-6 and H-6'), 6.93 (2H, d, J 1.64 Hz; H-4 and H-4'), 6.11 (2H, br. s; disappeared on deuterium exchange; $2 \times$ ArOH), 4.40 (4H, s; $2 \times$ Ar- CH_2 -OMe), 3.94 (6H, s; $2 \times$ ArOCH₃) and 3.39 (6H, s; $2 \times$ Ar- CH_2 -OCH₃).

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